

Influence of π -stacking along with hydrogen bonding interactions in the recognition of monocarboxylic acids[†]

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The new receptors 1 and 2 have been designed and synthesized where phenyl and naphthalene rings have been introduced in place of aliphatic chain in receptor 3 to achieve the π -stacking interactions. These receptors show higher association constants with aromatic over aliphatic carboxylic acids compared to receptor 3 which preferably recognizes long chain aliphatic acid.

Design and synthesis of artificial receptors that can achieve recognition at the molecular level is one of the major goals to mimic biological events both in organic and inorganic chemistry¹. For the fabrication of artificial receptors the basic interactions such as hydrogen bonding², CH- π interaction³, π -stacking effect⁴, the hydrophobic effect⁵ etc. have recently received considerable attention in the field of molecular recognition. In combination with the multiple interaction sites through hydrogen bonds, π -stacking effect sometimes plays a considerable role for the higher order of successful hetero-association of the host and guest. Participation of both hydrogen bonding and π -stacking interactions offers a rational approach for the recognition of aromatic acids⁶, amino acids⁷, planar heterocycles⁸ such as adenine, thymine etc. and the geometry of the π -stacking interaction groups (face to face or edge to face)⁹ is also of importance in DNA and protein crystal structures.

The binding of carboxylic acid or carboxylate groups is involved in many biological recognition processes. In bilirubin, formation of intramolecular three point hydrogen bonds¹⁰ with pyrrole and lactam functionalities of two propionic acid residues at two different carbons generate two interconverting enantiomers and amide-carboxylate binding in vancomycin¹¹ addresses the significance of the recognition of carboxylic acid.

Monocarboxylic acids are generally present in dimeric or in highly associated form and the dimerisation constant¹² is usually in the order of $5 \times 10^2 M^{-1}$. The dimeric form which is resonance stabilized is slightly converted to the

monomeric species at the high dilution in non polar solvent. Thus the design and synthesis of artificial receptors for the preferential recognition of monocarboxylic acids (aliphatic versus aromatic) by overcoming self-association is an interesting and difficult problem.

In continuation of our work on molecular recognition for biologically important substrates like monocarboxylic acid¹³, dicarboxylic acid¹⁴, urea¹⁵ etc., we wish to report here another class of molecular receptors (1 and 2) for the recognition of aromatic acids over aliphatic acids employing three point hydrogen bonding and π -stacking interactions and also a brief study of two point hydrogen bondings of carboxylic acids with receptors having different heterocyclic moieties (naphthyridine units in 5 and 6). The other designed receptor 7 was synthesized to examine the possible higher association with aliphatic monocarboxylic acids employing multiple contact points for the hydroxyl hydrogen of -COOH group.

Results and discussion

Previously we have studied the binding event with the monocarboxylic acids by the receptors 3 and 4 on the basis of the two point versus three point hydrogen bonding¹³. The experiment gave an insight about the preferential association of aliphatic acids over aromatic acids with receptor 3 in comparison to 4. Particularly, the receptor 3 which is presently studied shows higher association with long chain monocarboxylic acid (K_a for myristic acid is $4.10 \times 10^2 M^{-1}$). This higher binding constant may be explained

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probably due to the hydrophobic-hydrophobic interactions between the long chains of both the receptor and substrate or chain to chain stacking as proposed by Dannenberg *et al.* for acetic acid¹⁶

In the present study, the flexible aliphatic chain in receptor **3** has been replaced by phenyl and naphthyl groups (**1** and **2** respectively) and they are exploited to see the reverse phenomena, as occurred in receptor **3** i.e. towards the preferential binding of aromatic acids over aliphatic acids by addressing two weak basic forces, hydrogen bonding and π -stacking interactions.

Receptors **1** and **2** have been synthesized by high dilution reaction of two different amines with isophthalaloyl dichloride. For the receptor **1** the corresponding 4-octyloxy aniline was synthesized according to Scheme 1.

Reagents : (i) K_2CO_3 , dry DMF, octyl bromide, (ii) H_2 , Pd/C, EtOH.

Scheme 1

The other receptors **5** and **6** were prepared by the reported procedures¹⁷. NMR-titrations in $CDCl_3$ show moderate binding¹⁸ and formation of 1 : 1 complex with a number of aliphatic (propionic, myristic, ibuprofen, naproxen etc.) and aromatic acids with the simple receptors **1** and **2**. The considerable downfield shifts of both amide protons of phenyl (0.5–1.01 ppm)/naphthyl (0.7–0.9 ppm) amines as well as pyridine amide protons (1.00–3.00 ppm) in both

the receptors **1** and **2** show the evidence of the formation of three point hydrogen bonding in the complexation of carboxylic acids. This was also supported from IR studies¹³. Due to the insolubility of 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid and naproxen in $CDCl_3$, titration was carried out in $CDCl_3$ containing 1% d_6 -DMSO for better solubility though binding constant values are sacrificed to some extent using DMSO which is also a competitive binding partner.

From the comparative binding constant studies in Tables 1, 2 and 3, a marginal increase in the association constant of propionic acid with the receptors **1** and **2** may be due to the increase in acidity of the amide protons of the phenyl/naphthyl residues. Although for propionic acid, K_a values with receptors **1** and **2** are marginally increased, for myristic acid the binding constant value is decreased with both the receptors **1** and **2** compared to receptor **3**. This suggests an adverse steric effect probably imparted by the different conformations of the long chain. For benzoic and anisic acids with receptor **1**, K_a are increased by ~ 2 times compared to receptor **3** and receptor **2** is found to have K_a by ~ 2 times

Table 1. Binding constants with 1

Substrate acids	K_a (M^{-1})
Propionic	2.10×10^2
Myristic	2.27×10^2
Benzoic	2.50×10^2
Anisic	3.39×10^2
Ibuprofen	1.70×10^2
Naproxen	2.40×10^2
4-Nitrobenzoic acid	6.00×10^2
3,5-Dinitrobenzoic	4.01×10^3

Table 2. Binding constants with 2

Substrate acids	K_a (M^{-1})
Propionic	2.20×10^2
Myristic	1.90×10^2
Benzoic	4.66×10^2
Anisic	5.60×10^2
Ibuprofen	2.00×10^2
Naproxen	2.86×10^2
4-Nitrobenzoic acid	8.80×10^2
3,5-Dinitrobenzoic	2.97×10^3

Table 3. Binding constants with 3

Substrate acids	K_a (M^{-1})
Propionic	1.70×10^2
Myristic	4.10×10^2
Benzoic	1.34×10^2
Anisic	1.65×10^2
Ibuprofen	2.80×10^2

more in comparison to receptor **1** for the change of π -surface area from phenyl to naphthalene.

This enhancement in binding constants is best ascribed by the π -stacking phenomena that occur between the phenyl or naphthalene rings of the hosts and the phenyl rings of the guests in the complexes **8** and **9**. This π -stacking is recognized from ^1H NMR by upfield shift of the corresponding protons of the guest phenyl rings and the host phenyl/naphthalene rings by 0.05 to 0.3 ppm.

Electron deficient phenyl ring of 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid is complexed with much higher K_a value by the receptor **1** due to possible charge transfer contribution to the complex for the overlapping of the aromatic clouds as well as increasing acidity of the carboxylic acid group of the guest. This overlapping is probably disturbed in receptor **2** on complexation with 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid due to some steric factor exerted by the $-\text{NO}_2$ groups of the guest as well as naphthalene ring of the receptor and accordingly gives lower association constant. Due to lack of proper alignment of π -surface as well as some adverse steric effect present in the binding pocket for the $-\text{Me}$ group (at α -position with respect to $-\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ group) of ibuprofen, less binding affinity of both the receptors **1** and **2** with ibuprofen is observed. For the case of receptor **2** with ibuprofen, the only marginal increase is due to more overlapping of both π -surfaces for the naphthalene ring. But interestingly, naproxen binds with receptor **2** with a higher K_a value compared to ibuprofen although it has the similar structural adverse steric effect in binding zone and this may be accounted for more π -stacking stability for the two naphthalene rings.

Involvement of peri hydrogen of isophthaloyl unit in both the receptors **1** and **2** is recognized from its downfield chemical shift ($\Delta\delta$ 0.01–0.20 ppm) during the complex formation with carboxylic acids. For the aromatic acids, the shift is more whereas in the case of aliphatic acids the shifts are less. Interestingly, peri proton of the receptor **3** on

complexation with benzoic acid underwent a downfield chemical shift of 0.09 ppm whereas in the receptors **1** and **2**, the shift of peri protons are 0.16 and 0.14 ppm respectively. This higher downfield shift from the receptor **3** to receptor **1** may be explained due to the favourable orientation of the carboxylic carbonyl group with the peri hydrogen by the organisational influence of π -stacking groups of the receptor and the substrate.

The alignment of the π -surfaces during the complexation of the aromatic monocarboxylic acids with receptors **1** and **2** were realized from the docked structures¹⁹ of the receptor-substrate complex (Fig. 1). Docking experiments were

Fig. 1. Docking structures.

performed by taking receptors **1** and **2** with both electron rich and electron deficient guests. The stabilization energies are reported in Table 4. Depending on the electronic environment of the receptors and the guests, the geometries of the complexes are found to be different.

Table 4. Energy values (kJ/mol) of the docking complexes			
	Benzoic acid	Anisic acid	4-Nitrobenzoic acid
Receptor 1	-64.48	-86.03	-70.86
Receptor 2	-52.51	-52.41	-51.28

On the other hand, for further increase in the binding affinities of the receptor **3** with aliphatic acids the receptor **3** has been modified to receptor **7** where naphthyridine moiety is taken instead of pyridine moiety to get a multiple contact of hydroxyl hydrogen of $-\text{COOH}$ group with the peri lone pairs of the naphthyridine ring nitrogens. Surprisingly, the simultaneous participation of peri lone pairs of naphthyridine 1,8-nitrogens to make a stronger hydrogen bonded structure (Fig. 2) is not effective as is observed in binding experi-

ment with naphthyridine receptor **5** and benzoic acid.

Fig. 2

Actually it weakens the binding (e.g. K_a for benzoic acid = $62 M^{-1}$) compared to simple pyridine amide unit **4** (K_a for benzoic acid = $230 M^{-1}$). This reduction in binding constant values can be explained due to negative secondary hydrogen bonding interaction as proposed by Jorgensen²⁰ as well as reduced basicity of naphthyridine ring nitrogens compared to pyridine ring nitrogen in **4**. It is also evident that the other naphthyridine system **6** (Fig. 2) is also unable to achieve a higher association over the receptor **4** (e.g. K_a for benzoic acid = $170 M^{-1}$) which is probably due to its strong self-associated form as well as its tautomerisation to the enol form **6a** (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3

Based on these relative information, receptor **7** was still used to check its binding affinity with aliphatic carboxylic acids (K_a for propionic acid = $90 M^{-1}$). However, due to this weak binding, receptor **7** was not further explored. This sort of experiment makes the receptor **3** unique for the aliphatic acids and also makes the simple pyridine amide moiety **4** superior as a two point binding partner in comparison to other alternatives (**5** and **6**).

In conclusion it may be stated that the model receptors **1** and **2**, capable of making three point hydrogen bonds with carboxylic acids, preferably recognizes the aromatic acids over the aliphatic acids by the influence of both hydrogen bonding as well as π -stacking interactions within the isophthaloyl spacer by changing the long aliphatic chain by aromatic rings (phenyl/naphthyl) in receptor **3** which prefers aliphatic acids, specially long chain fatty acids.

Experimental

General : All solvents were dried prior to use. Silica gel chromatography was performed using 60–120 mesh. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Model-883 and 1H NMR spectra are recorded on a Bruker AM 200. Melting points were recorded in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

4-Octyloxy nitrobenzene : *p*-Nitrophenol (1 g; 7.19 mmol), K_2CO_3 (2.48 g; 17.9 mmol) were taken in dry DMF and stirred at room temperature for 15 mins. Then a solution of octyl bromide (1.38 g; 7.19 mmol) was added to the mixture and stirring was continued over night. The residue was taken up in water and poured into a separator funnel. Then it was thoroughly washed by water and the aqueous layer was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 . The combined organic phase were dried (Na_2SO_4), filtered and concentrated in vacuum to give a thick yellowish brown liquid (90% yield) which was of higher purity for the next run. 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 8.18 (2H, d, J 10 Hz), 6.91 (2H, d, J 10 Hz), 4.02 (2H, t, J 6 Hz), 1.82 (2H, m), 1.49–1.30 (10H, m), 0.90 (3H, t, J 6.3 Hz).

4-Octyloxy aniline : A mixture of compound 4-octyloxy nitrobenzene (0.50 g; 2 mmol) and 10% Pd/C (0.1 g) in ethanol was stirred at room temperature under H_2 atmosphere for overnight. Catalyst was filtered off and the solvent, evaporated in vacuo to give crude product in 95% yield which was almost pure for the preparation of the receptor **1**.

1-[[[6-Methylpyrid-2-yl)amino]carbonyl]-3-[(4-octyloxy aniline) carbonyl] benzene (1) :

A solution of 2-amino-6-methyl pyridine (105 mg; 0.98 mmol) and triethylamine (0.1 ml) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (15 ml) and a solution of 4-octyloxy aniline (216 mg; 0.98 mmol) and triethylamine (0.1 ml) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (15 ml) were simultaneously added dropwise separately from two dropping funnels to isophthaloyl dichloride (200 mg; 0.98 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (20 ml) under nitrogen during a period of 1 h, the whole mixture was then stirred overnight. Then the mixture washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate followed by water. The separated organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 and evaporated to dryness. The crude mixture was purified by preparative layer chromatography (20% EtOAc in $CHCl_3$) to afford the receptor **1** which was analytically pure by passing through a short silica gel column as white solid (206 mg; 45%), m.p. 160° . IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3309, 3055, 1978, 1820, 1721, 1649 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 8.66 [1H, s, NH (pyr. amide)], 8.42 (1H, s), 8.20–8.08 (3H, m), 7.91 [1H, s, NH (benz)], 7.67 (1H, t, J 8 Hz), 7.59–

7.53 (3H, m), 6.96 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 6.91 (2H, d, J 8 Hz), 3.96 (2H, t, J 6 Hz), 2.49 (3H, s), 1.85–1.71 (4H, m), 1.30–1.25 (8H, m), 0.88 (3H, t, J 6 Hz); ^{13}C (CDCl_3) δ 164.79, 164.47, 156.37, 150.58, 139.05, 135.66, 134.56, 131.31, 130.60, 130.24, 129.46, 125.37, 122.33, 122.21, 119.77, 117.31, 114.88, 111.19, 68.32, 31.82, 29.70, 29.37, 26.04, 25.04, 23.86, 14.12, MS, (EI, m/e) M^+ 460.4 (32.55%) (Found : C, 73.03; H, 7.01; N, 8.98. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 73.22; H, 7.18; N, 9.14).

1-[[[(6-Methylpyrid-2-yl)amino]carbonyl]-3-[(naphthylamino) carbonyl]benzene (2) :

Following the same procedure as done for the receptor **1**, 2-amino-6-methylpyridine (37.7 mg; 0.34 mmol), 2-naphthylamine (50 mg; 0.34 mmol) and isophthaloyl dichloride (70.9 mg; 0.34 mmol) were taken to afford the product, purified by column chromatography (20% EtOAc in CHCl_3) in 48% (63.8 mg) yield, m.p. 179°. IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3465, 3280, 3050, 2915, 1649, 1596, 1574 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 8.80 [1H, s, NH (pyr. amide)], 8.51 (1H, s), 8.38 (1H, s), 8.28 [1H, s, NH (naphthyl amide)], 8.22–8.11(3H, m), 7.84 (3H, m), 7.68 (3H, m), 7.46 (2H, m), 6.97 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 2.50 (3H, s), MS, m/e M^+ 381, 346, 274, 239, 212, 135, 97 (Found : C, 74.10; H, 4.92; N, 10.91. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 75.56; H, 5.02; N, 11.02).

1-[[[(7-Methylnaphthyrid-2-yl)amino]-3-[dodecyl carbonyl] benzene (7) :

To a stirred solution of isophthaloyl dichloride (127.5 mg; 0.63 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (40 ml) both 2-amino-7-methylnaphthyridine (100 mg; 0.63 mmol) and dodecyl amine (116.5 mg; 0.63 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 were added simultaneously and stirring was continued overnight. The final mixture was washed with saturated NaHCO_3 and water thoroughly. The organic solvent was then evaporated in vacuo and was purified by column chromatography using 5% MeOH in CHCl_3 to afford the product (163 mg; 55%), m.p. 152°. ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 9.21 [1H, s, NH (naphthyridine amide)], 8.62 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 8.20 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 8.08 (3H, m), 7.61(1H, t, J 8 Hz), 7.29 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 6.40 [1H, bs, NH (dodecyl amide)], 3.48 (2H, q, $-\text{NHCH}_2$, J 6.6 Hz), 2.58 (3H, s), 1.66–1.57 (4H, m, $-\text{NHCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2$), 1.36–1.26 [16H, m, $(\text{CH}_2)_8$], 0.88 (3H, t, J 6 Hz), MS, m/e M^+ 474.

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